

GRAPH-BASED VISUALIZED MODEL: AN IDEAL ALTERNATIVE FOR TEMPORAL ANOMALY DETECTION IN OLD PEOPLE'S HOME

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Abstract

The need to have a secure lifestyle for older persons at home is in demand more than ever. One of the major concerns for smart home systems is the capability of adapting to the user as personalizing the behaviour of the home may provide improved comfort, control, and safety. The main aim of this work is to simulate a graph-based visualized model for temporal anomaly detection in smart homes which can be applicable in building occupant specific smart homes. To achieve this goal, dataset of activities of daily living from a smart environment covering a period of 60 days was used. The data covered in this 60day period consist of three non-repetitive daily routine activities, with specifics to the *start_time* and duration was used for building the trend / pattern of which a deviation from this trend implies an anomaly. The result of the study revealed that line plot and scatter plot graph can be used to create a graph-based models for temporal anomaly detection in old people's home. This is a visualized system with the advantages of flexibility, speed and lack of need for label attribute.

Keywords: Graph-based visualized model, temporal anomaly detection, Old people's home, smart environments, Smart home system

1. Introduction

The need for graph-based model has become important in different areas of detecting patters and anomalies. However, no much work has been in this area [1]. Studying and mimicking human behaviour is a great asset for computer systems. It provides knowledge of human behaviour and the impact on their overall wellbeing. Hence, computerized systems focusing on human behaviour require adequate information from humans. The need for the development of computerized systems like smart homes, health monitoring and energy efficiency is dependent on the cost of health services, sustainability and age of the population [2].

This birthed the evolution of wireless, modest and affordable sensors for information collation in daily 'smart' surroundings. This information so collected when studied using machine learning techniques, do not only give discernment that can be inter-leavened in our

lives but can also produce computerized domain specific support to daily living environments, for example a smart home [3].

In reality, embedded sensors in the smart home produces data as occupant's carryout everyday routines. The data is usually gathered via a computer network which acts as a bridge and is housed in a database that the informant uses to produce insight-like trends and make prediction which is conveyed via the network to physical devices that executes a trigger, for a corresponding action or human intervention [4].

In addition to the identification of normal activities that make up for the majority of sensor events produced, occupants of smart homes are also interested in anomalies which may reflect a crisis associated with health challenges, security monitoring where suspicious activities are flagged. Hence, anomaly detection is most assured when based on behaviours that are predictable and regular [5].

Smart Technologies and Homes can be taken a step further by analyzing the daily routine activities of its occupants and comparing such over time. A behavioural pattern can thus be established and deviations from this established pattern(s) considered an abnormal behaviour [6].

This paper aims at simulating a graph-based model for temporal anomaly detection in smart homes which can be applicable in building occupant specific smart homes. To achieve this goal, dataset of activities of daily living from a smart environment covering a period of 60 days was used. The data covered in this 60day period consist of three non-repetitive daily routine activities, with specifics to the start_time and duration was used for building the trend / pattern of which a deviation from this trend implies an anomaly precisely the first part of the occupant's day before leaving home. This trend / pattern created is based on the start_time and duration of each of this activity and collectively becomes the model/template for normalcy of which a deviation from this trend implies an anomaly.

2. Related work

Steiger et al, proposed a visualization system for interactive pattern analysis in univariate sensor networks particularly anomaly detection with focus on the analysis of similar patterns over different temporal scales. The methods used were best practices in the information visualization domain which cover the daily, weekly and seasonal patterns of data with the daily collections being analyzed in a clustering-based view [7].

Paudel, proposed that a graph-based approach can successfully discover patterns and anomalies in resident activities. Activity graphs were constructed from smart home daily activities to detect normative patterns as well as spatial and behavioural anomalies [8].

Eberle and Holder proposed a graph-based approach in uncovering anomalies in domains where anomalies consist of unexpected entity/relationship deviations that resemble non-anomalous behaviour using synthetic and real-world data [1].

Reveiro and Falkman, also agreed that visualization can contribute to the data mining process by its ability to represent results of complex computational algorithms, ability to depict the process and discover complex patterns which cannot be automatically detected, however, using the powerful human visual system, it can be detected [9].

Research in anomaly detection has proposed lots of solutions to effectively detect anomaly which can be behavioural, spatial and temporal for both categorical and continuous datasets. In this paper the trends / patterns model, I derived was used as basis for anomaly detection.

3. Methodology

The data used in this project [10], was gotten from the online repository which consist sensor events data collated from the Washington State University, Centre for Advanced Studies in Adaptive Systems (WSU CASAS) Tulin smart apartment test bed from April to July of 2009. The apartment houses two married residents, though record of only one occupant is made public in this release. The original data had ten generic activities of both repetitive and non-repetitive activity of daily living, annotated by *start_time* and *end_time* of each routine activity occurrence having four attributes.

Figure 1 Phases in the Data Handling Work Flow

The data collected from the WSU CASAS online repository, was a text file and needed to be prepared by uploading it through the xlminer platform via the import text wizard. This action have passed through the phases of data handling as shown in figure 1, that is its collection, preparation, representation was done by converting the data from text file format into rows and columns. It resulted to 486,912 rows with 6 columns. This resulting dataset in the xlminer format allowed for sorting and feature extraction and visualization for activities of daily living with its corresponding *start time*, *end time*, its state that is *'begin'* or *'end'* per day. The duration(mins) which is the core of this study, was derived by invoking the function *MINUTE()*, to convert the result of the difference between the *start* and *end* time.

4. Implementation

In the implementation that is the visualization phase, which is the last phase in the data handling work flow shown in figure 1, xlminer, the tool was used for creating the graph-based visualized model. XLMiner is a wide range tool offering various methods in investigating data with an all-inclusive machine-learning and statistical techniques for classification, prediction, affinity analysis, data exploration and reduction [11]. XLMiner is part of the Analytic integrated software for predictive and prescriptive analytics like

forecasting, data mining, optimization and simulation. This gives Excel the capacity to solve both small and big data problems and every business analyst uses Excel because it often plays a role in many analytical projects [11].

XLMiner’s data mining algorithms, now written in C++, were based on studies of the latest published papers, doctoral theses and conference proceedings in machine learning and data mining. All directed to take utmost advantage of multi-core processors and modern vector instruction sets. This resulted in a dramatic upgrade in performance (often 100 times faster or more) and capability to manage large, composite datasets. A performance benchmark of the XLMiner against software packages such as SAS JMP, IBM SPSS and Minitab was carried out to ensure that XLMiner could handle datasets as large as these well-known statistical packages, with similar or better performance.

As shown in figure 2 and figure 3, the times series and scatter plot graph were both used to implement the graph-based model. These models created, reveals the trend of the occupant’s daily first three non-repetitive routine activities of daily living for a 60 day period.

Figure 2: Simulated Time Series Model

Figure 3: Simulated Bubble Chart Model

Figure 4, 5 and 6 on the other hand gives a more detailed singular view of the normal pattern for the cook_breakfast individual activity of daily living at a weekly level. This pattern or trend shows that the normal time duration for the cook_breakfast activity as a minimum of 5 minutes and maximum of 35 minutes.

Figure 4: Simulated ADL_Cook_Breakfast Model Week 1

Figure 5: Simulated ADL_Cook_Breakfast Model Week 2

Figure 6: Simulated ADL_Cook_Breakfast Model Week 3

However, Figure 7 and 8 reveals the anomaly based on the condition of 5 minutes minimum and 35 minutes maximum for this particular activity. This is seen in days 25, 29 and 30. Day 25 has a duration less than lower limit of 5 minutes while Day 29 and 30 has duration higher than the higher limit.

Figure 7: Simulated ADL_Cook_Breakfast Model Week 4

Figure 8: Simulated ADL_Cook_Breakfast Model Week 5

5. Result

The result of the model built in figure 2 as shown in figure 3, reveals that both line plot and scatter plot graphs can be used to create graph-based models for temporal anomaly detection in old people's home, which is a visualized system and has the advantages of flexibility, speed and lack of need for label attribute/value. This discovery is in agreement with Paudel et al, Eberle and Holder, that a graph-based approach can successfully discover patterns and anomalies in resident activities and Steiger et al, on the use of a visualization system for interactive pattern analysis.

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